

An Evolving Engagement of the EU Agency for the Space Programme in Space Security

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Abstract

The EU Space Programme integrates security and defence considerations, marking a significant transformation in the Union’s strategic posture and strategic autonomy, reducing dependence on non-EU space systems and ensuring uninterrupted access to critical space-based services. At the heart of this evolution lies the European Union Space Programme and European Union Agency for the Space Programme (EUSPA). EUSPA has a central role in the operational management of the EU Space Programme, and a pivotal role in the space security of the EU space assets while supporting the emergence of safety and security-related applications. This article provides an overview of the evolving role of the European Union Agency for the Space Programme (EUSPA) in space security.

Keywords:

Space Security, EU Space Programme, EUSPA, Strategic Autonomy, Space Infrastructure

1. Introduction

Space has become part of everyday life, offering a multitude of applications and services. It can serve as an enabler for sectorial policies. These include agriculture, fisheries, transport, energy, urban development, environment, climate change, etc. Space technologies and applications also support safety, security, and defence. It can assist in disaster management, search and rescue, border monitoring and control, etc. which currently occupies decision and policy makers with the overall geopolitical setting.

Space security is a concept that has been evolving over the past few years with no universally accepted definition. Traditionally, it has been defined as the ability to access and use space for all nations. However, with the increase in space activity and the development of new technologies, the concept of space security has been broadened to include the protection of space assets and the prevention of an arms race in space. The policies and strategies of the European Union (EU) outline the concept as encompassing the protection of space-based assets, ensuring the resilience of space systems, and safeguarding the interests of the EU and its Member States in the space domain (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The seamless chain of citizens protection encompassing safety, security and defence.

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The EU Space Programme integrates security and defence considerations, marking a significant transformation in the Union's strategic posture. At the heart of this evolution lies the European Union Space Programme and European Union Agency for the Space Programme (EUSPA)¹. EUSPA has a central role in the operational management of the EU Space Programme, and a pivotal role in the space security of the EU space assets while supporting the emergence of safety and security-related applications. This shift aligns with broader EU policy initiatives, including the 2022 Strategic Compass for Security and Defence² and the 2023 EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence (EUSSD)³, both of which underscore space as a strategic domain critical to the Union's resilience, autonomy, and security^{2,3}. The integration of security elements enhances the resilience of EU space infrastructure against emerging threats, including cyberattacks, space debris proliferation, and counterspace capabilities.

Against this backdrop, this paper provides an introduction to the EU Space Programme and the EU Agency for the Space Programme and highlights specific elements related to space security. Moreover, the analysis delves into the specific activities in space technologies and services for space security. Furthermore, this study contributes to the broader discourse on the EU's strategic autonomy in space and its capacity to safeguard critical space infrastructure in an increasingly contested environment.

2. The EU in space

2.1 EU space framework

The European Union (EU) has increased over the years its engagement in the space landscape. Historically, the EU's engagement in space activities was primarily oriented towards the enhancement of technological innovation and industrial competitiveness. This orientation mirrored the broader tenets of European integration, prioritizing economic expansion and scientific advancement.

The Lisbon Treaty, which came into force on December 1, 2009⁴ provides the first explicit legal basis for EU action in space. Article 189 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) granted the EU competence in particular in drawing up a European space policy (Art. 189.1); establish the necessary measures which may take the form of a European space programme (Art. 189.2) and establish appropriate relations with the European Space Agency (ESA). Today the EU has set up an elaborate framework based on Art. 189 (Table 1).

Dec 2009	The Lisbon Treaty, Article 189
Apr 2011	<i>Communication [COM(2011) 152] "Towards a space strategy for the European Union that benefits its citizens"</i>
Oct 2016	<i>Communication [COM(2016)705 final] "Space Strategy for Europe"</i>
Oct 2016	<i>Joint statement on shared vision and goals for the future of Europe in space by the EU and ESA</i>
April 2021	<i>Regulation (EU) 2021/696 establishing the EU Space Programme and the European Union Agency for the Space Programme.</i>
Feb 2022	<i>Joint Communication [JOINT(2022) 4] "An EU Approach for Space Traffic Management"</i>
June 2022	<i>Financial Framework Partnership Agreement (FFPA) between EC, ESA, EUSPA</i>

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Mar 2023	Regulation (EU) 2023/588 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2023 establishing the Union Secure Connectivity Programme for the period 2023-2027
Mar 2023	Joint Communication [JOINT (2023) 9] “European Union Space Strategy for Security and Defence”

Table 1: Main documents of the EU space framework after the Lisbon treaty

The changing geopolitical environment has prompted the EU to reconsider its strategy for space. Over the past two decades, space has increasingly become a competitive and strategic area, necessitating the integration of security goals into what was once a primarily civilian-focused policy. This changing environment has gradually brought security issues into the EU's space policy, most recently demonstrated by the 2022 Strategic Compass for Security and Defence ² and the 2023 EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence ³.

2.2 Union Space Programme

The Union Space Programme, under Regulation (EU) 2021/696, ¹ consolidates all space-related activities under a single framework. With a budget for the period 2021 to 2027 of €14.8 billion, it surpasses previous investments, reflecting the increasing importance of space in European security and competitiveness.

2.2.1 Galileo and EGNOS

The involvement of the EU in the Galileo project was defined in its initial stage through a Council Resolution in 1999 ²¹. The first phase of Galileo went from 2003 to 2005, when the first experimental satellite, GIOVE-A, was launched. Galileo kept developing and in 2008 GIOVE-B was launched, followed by the first two In-Orbit Validation (IOV) satellites in 2011, as well as the first two Full Operational Capability (FOC) satellites in 2014 ⁵.

In 2016 Galileo entered into Initial Services. Since then, billions of people worldwide with a Galileo enabled device have been able to use its signals for positioning, navigation and timing. This was a milestone that corresponded to the availability of the first operations of the Open Service (OS), Public Regulated Service (PRS), and Search and Rescue (SAR) services. In December 2016, EUSPA (then GSA) became the service operator for Galileo. Later in 2019, the phase of Enhanced Services started, which implemented the OS Positioning for improved navigation performances, and made available the SAR Return Link Service (RLS).

The Open Service FOC phase is now under preparation, and it will mark the availability of the various services in their final configuration. The Initial Operational Capability of the Public Regulated Service is under preparation, and the new OSNMA (Authenticated-Open Service) is under testing. The High Accuracy Service (HAS) was declared operational in 2023, and its evolution is under preparation.

The launch of the EGNOS Programme was approved by the European Council in 1994. It was confirmed to be a component of Europe's satellite navigation policy in 2003. In 2005, the version 1 (v1) of the system started its initial operations phase, followed by the v2.1 which implemented the EGNOS Data Server, while the v2.2 allowed for an extended coverage through the Regional Extension Module concept. In 2009, EGNOS assets were transferred from ESA to the European Commission, and the OS was declared operational; since 2014 the EGNOS exploitation has been delivered by EUSPA (previously GSA) under delegation from the European Commission. In 2018 a contract was signed for the development of the next version of EGNOS ⁵.

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2.2.2 Copernicus

Copernicus was born from the idea of creating a European environment monitoring programme, agreed upon in 1998. The programme was initially introduced as “Global Monitoring for Environmental Security”; then, in 2004, a space-based observation component was proposed, therefore the European Commission and ESA signed an agreement setting the stage for the Sentinel satellites family. In 2011, the Initial Operation phase began, and the programme was renamed Copernicus the subsequent year. The deployment of the space component began in 2014 with the launch of Sentinel 1-A radar satellite and continues until today,⁷ carrying on a process aiming to place a complete constellation of almost 20 satellites in orbit before 2030⁸. EUSPA has undertaken various market uptake activities in Copernicus since 2021.

2.2.3 GOVSATCOM and IRIS²

The implementation of the GOVSATCOM component of the EU Space Programme started in 2021, under the new Space Programme Regulation, while the GOVSATCOM Preparatory Action was initiated by the European Parliament already in 2020. The GOVSATCOM will use the capacities and services provided by existing national satcom systems and accredited private operators⁹.

The Union Secure Connectivity Programme, the so-called IRIS², under Regulation (EU) 2023/588¹⁰ aims to deliver secure, autonomous, reliable, and cost-effective satellite communication services to government-authorized users, enhancing the Union's resilience, autonomy, and technological and industrial base in satellite communication. The programme will be implemented in phases, focusing on developing space and ground infrastructure for governmental services, while also enabling commercial services by the private sector, thereby fostering innovation and competitiveness in the European space industry. The programme integrating and complementing existing and future national and European capacities in the framework of the GOVSATCOM component, and developing further and gradually integrating the European Quantum Communication Infrastructure (EuroQCI) initiative into the secure connectivity system¹.

2.2.4 Space Situational Awareness (SSA)

The Space Situational Awareness (SSA) component of the EU Space Programme means a high-level comprehensive approach to hazards in space which could harm space-based or ground-based infrastructure or endanger any activity in, or going to, space, or which could endanger life or health. It includes the following sub-components: (i) ‘SST sub-component’, a space surveillance and tracking system aiming to improve, operate and provide data, information and services related to the surveillance and tracking of space objects that orbit the Earth; (ii) ‘SWE sub-component’, observational parameters related to space weather events; and (iii) ‘NEO sub-component’, the risk monitoring of near-Earth objects approaching the Earth.

2.3 EU Space Programme and services

The EU Space Programme plays a multifaceted role in safety and security due to its multipurposed nature. The programme contributes to the EU's strategic autonomy in the space domain, reducing dependence on non-EU space systems and ensuring uninterrupted access to critical space-based services. In particular, a number of services provided relate to space security.

2.3.1 Galileo Services

Galileo, the European Union's global navigation satellite system (GNSS), offers a suite of services designed to cater to a wide range of users, from the general public to specialized sectors. These services are crucial for positioning, navigation, and timing (PNT) applications, and are integral to various aspects of modern life, including transportation, emergency response, and scientific research. Several services are developed or are under development.

¹ REF [10], Art.10, L79/3

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2.3.1.1 Open Service (OS)

The OS is a free-of-charge service designed for mass-market applications. It provides positioning, navigation, and timing information to users with Galileo-enabled devices. The OS is fundamental for everyday applications such as smartphone navigation, location-based services, and is included in various consumer electronics. Its open nature ensures widespread accessibility and fosters innovation in related industries. The OS has a significant role in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of GNSS in urban environments and challenging signal conditions, contributing to the broader field of ubiquitous positioning.

2.3.1.2 Public Regulated Service (PRS)

The PRS is an encrypted service designed for authorized governmental users, such as law enforcement, emergency services, and critical infrastructure operators. It offers robust and secure PNT information, resistant to jamming and spoofing. The PRS is crucial for national security and sensitive applications where integrity and confidentiality are paramount. Its secure nature safeguards critical operations against potential threats. The PRS employs cryptographic techniques enhancing the resilience of governmental operations in the face of evolving security challenges.

2.3.1.3 Search and Rescue Service (SAR)

The SAR service contributes to the international Cospas-Sarsat system, which aids in locating and rescuing people in distress. Galileo's SAR service provides faster and more accurate detection of distress signals, and also provides an important and unique Return Link Service (RLS) (Figure 2). The SAR service plays a vital role in saving lives by significantly reducing the time it takes to locate individuals in emergency situations. The RLS, a distinctive feature of Galileo, provides feedback to the person in distress, confirming that their signal has been received. The SAR service contributed to improving emergency response times and enhancing the overall effectiveness of search and rescue operations, particularly in remote or challenging environments.

Figure 2: Galileo Search and Rescue (SAR) Return Link Service (RLS) (Source: EUSPA)

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2.3.1.4 High Accuracy Service (HAS)

The HAS is a commercial service that provides high-accuracy positioning information, with accuracy down to centimetres. It is designed for professional applications requiring precise location data, such as surveying, precision agriculture, and autonomous driving. The HAS caters to the growing demand for high-precision PNT solutions in various sectors, enabling advancements in autonomous systems and location-based services. There are technical aspects incorporated for achieving high accuracy in GNSS, including the use of precise point positioning (PPP) techniques and advanced signal processing algorithms, which are fundamental to the HAS (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Galileo High Accuracy Service (HAS) (source: EUSPA)

2.3.1.5 Signal Service-Authentication (SAS)

Signal Authentication service (SAS) is understood as the ability to provide a level of guarantee to users regarding the use of signals and data from actual Galileo satellites and not from any other source. This capacity will increase the degree of trust on the services based on Galileo positioning and prevent spoofing of Galileo signals, which may lead to committing fraud. The purpose of this service is to satisfy the demand of GNSS users and applications of a trusted navigation solution provided by GNSS systems.

2.3.1.6 Emergency Warning Service (EWS)

The EWS is designed to broadcast emergency warnings to users in affected areas, providing timely information about natural disasters or other critical events. It is based on the Return Link Service (RLS) capabilities of Galileo satellites. The EWS plays a crucial role in enhancing disaster preparedness and response, enabling timely dissemination of warnings to potentially affected populations. There are activities ongoing that are further developing the integration of GNSS with early warning systems and the development of effective communication strategies for disseminating emergency information.

Figure 4: Emergency Warning Service (EWS) based on the Return Link Service (RLS) (Source: EUSPA)

2.3.2 EGNOS Services

The European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS) is a satellite-based augmentation system (SBAS) that improves the accuracy and reliability of GPS signals over Europe. It plays a crucial role in enhancing the performance of Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) for various applications, particularly in safety-critical domains. Several services are developed or are under development.

2.3.2.1 Open Service (OS)

The OS is a free-of-charge service that enhances the accuracy of GNSS positioning for general users. Today, it provides corrections and integrity information to improve the performance of GPS signals. The OS benefits a wide range of applications, including consumer navigation, location-based services, and general positioning needs. By improving accuracy, it enhances the user experience and enables more precise location determination. The OS plays a role in mitigating errors inherent in GPS signals, such as ionospheric and tropospheric delays, thereby improving positioning accuracy and reliability for mass-market applications.

2.3.2.2 Safety of Life Service (SoL)

The SoL service is designed for safety-critical applications, such as civil aviation. It provides high-integrity information to ensure the reliability of GNSS signals for operations where safety is paramount. The SoL service is essential for aviation, enabling the use of GNSS for precision approaches and other critical operations. It adheres to stringent international standards, such as those set by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), to ensure the safety of air navigation. The SoL service plays a role in enhancing the safety and efficiency of air traffic management. It is crucial in enabling the transition to performance-based navigation (PBN) and supporting the development of advanced air traffic management systems.

2.3.2.3 EGNOS Data Access Service (EDAS)

EDAS is a commercial service that provides access to EGNOS data through the internet. It offers high-quality data for professional and commercial applications requiring precise positioning and timing information. EDAS caters to users who need reliable and accurate data for specialised applications, such as surveying, precision agriculture, and maritime navigation. It provides a

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convenient and efficient way to access EGNOS data for various professional needs. There are various developments of data processing techniques and algorithms for utilizing EGNOS data in high-precision applications. EDAS facilitates the integration of EGNOS data into various commercial and scientific tools.

2.3.3 Copernicus Services

Copernicus, the European Union's Earth Observation and Monitoring programme, provides free and open access to a wealth of data about our planet. It plays a crucial role in understanding and addressing environmental challenges, supporting policy-making, and fostering innovation in various sectors.

2.3.3.1 Atmosphere Monitoring

This service provides information on air quality, atmospheric composition, ozone layer and ultraviolet radiation, emissions and surface fluxes, solar radiation, and climate forcing. It supports air quality monitoring and forecasting, climate change research, and the development of policies to mitigate air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Atmospheric monitoring is essential in understanding the complex interactions between human activities and the environment. Copernicus data contributes to studies on air pollution, climate change, and atmospheric chemistry.

2.3.3.2 Marine Monitoring

This service provides information on the forecasting of ocean state for improved maritime safety, marine resources, coastal and marine environment, and ocean and climate. It supports maritime operations, fisheries management, coastal zone management, and climate change research related to the oceans. Marine monitoring plays an important role in understanding ocean dynamics, marine ecosystems, and the impacts of climate change on the oceans. Copernicus data contributes to research on ocean currents, sea level rise, and marine biodiversity.

2.3.3.3 Land Monitoring

This service provides information on systematic monitoring of biophysical parameters, land cover and land use mapping, thematic hot-spot mapping, and imagery and reference data. It supports agriculture, forestry, urban planning, and environmental monitoring. Copernicus data contribute to land use mapping, vegetation monitoring, and the assessment of natural resources. Land monitoring plays a role in understanding land use change, deforestation, and the impacts of agriculture on the environment. Copernicus data contribute to studies on land degradation, desertification, and sustainable land management.

2.3.3.4 Climate Change Monitoring

This service provides information on climate observations, reanalysis, forecasts and projections, data, tools and best practices supporting climate assessments, adaptation and mitigation. It supports climate change research, policy-making, and the development of adaptation and mitigation strategies. Copernicus data contributes to climate modelling, sea level rise monitoring, and the assessment of climate change impacts. Climate change monitoring plays a role in understanding the Earth's climate system, predicting future climate scenarios, and assessing the impacts of climate change on society and ecosystems. Copernicus data contributes to research on climate variability, extreme weather events, and climate change adaptation.

2.3.3.5 Security Monitoring

This service provides information on border surveillance, maritime surveillance, and support to EU security actions. It supports border management, maritime security, and the monitoring of security threats. Copernicus data contribute to the detection of illegal activities, the monitoring of maritime traffic, and the assessment of security risks. Security monitoring plays a role in addressing security challenges, such as illegal immigration, piracy, and terrorism. Copernicus data contribute to the development of early warning systems and the assessment of security vulnerabilities.

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2.3.3.6 Emergency Management Service (EMS)

This service provides on-demand mapping (all phases of the disaster management cycle), early warning and monitoring service (for floods, wildfires, droughts), and exposure mapping (different indicators for exposure). It supports disaster preparedness, response, and recovery. Copernicus data contribute to the mapping of disaster-affected areas, the monitoring of natural hazards, and the assessment of disaster risks. Emergency management plays a role in reducing disaster risks and enhancing disaster resilience. Copernicus data contribute to the development of early warning systems, the assessment of disaster impacts, and the planning of disaster response and recovery operations.

2.3.4 GovSatCom Services

GovSatCom is designed to provide a suite of secure and reliable communication services tailored for governmental users. These services address a wide range of critical applications, from crisis management and surveillance to the protection of critical infrastructure. GovSatCom is integral to ensuring the EU's strategic autonomy in secure communications, offering capabilities that are essential for national security and defence. The service portfolio, as defined by Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2023/1054, comprises three core service categories ¹¹:

2.3.4.1 End-to-end services

These services allow the user to connect to a satellite network that can provide the required user-to-user connectivity services (Mbps) typically based on SLAs. This means the governmental customers can access to a complete end-to-end communication solution including their satellite terminal without needing to set up their own infrastructure. Under this service modality, also known as managed services. The satellite service provider handles all aspects of the satellite communications to ensure the delivery of assured Mbps.

2.3.4.2 Raw capacity services

These services allow the users to utilise satellite capacity (bandwidth in MHz). An example of this would be a military unit using satellite capacity (MHz) to transmit data from a drone. The military user would be responsible for setting up and managing the satcom ground infrastructure, the drone terminal and the communication link between the drone and the satellite.

2.1.1.1 Anchored capacity services

This service, also known as teleport or uplink facilities, can complement raw capacity services with additional satellite communications ground infrastructure and be also embedded as part of the end-to-end services category. It can be then comprised of raw satellite capacity and ground station facilities provided by the service provider. The user has the flexibility to install its own ground equipment (e.g. network, baseband equipment) and establish its network and communication links with the satellite terminals.

The service's architecture, which includes a 'Common Union Pool' and a token-based compensation mechanism, allows for flexibility and prioritization in service allocation. This approach not only optimises resource utilisation but also reinforces the EU's capacity to respond effectively to security challenges, underscoring the program's significance in the European security framework. Govsatcom services will be accessible through the Govsatcom Hub currently under development. Each participating EU Member State will have a designated authority Competent Govsatcom Authority (CGA) to manage its requests and interactions with the GOVSATCOM hub (Figure 5).

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Figure 5: The Govsatcom service provision (Source: EUSPA)

2.1.2 Space Situational Awareness Services

Space Situational Awareness (SSA) is a critical capability for ensuring the long-term safety and sustainability of activities in space. By providing data, information, and services related to the space environment, SSA enables informed decision-making to mitigate potential risks and protect space-based assets. The SSA framework encompasses the following key components:

2.1.2.1 Space Surveillance and Tracking (SST)

SST involves the detection, tracking, and cataloguing of artificial objects orbiting Earth, including active and inactive satellites, rocket bodies, and debris, to help prevent collisions between space objects, predict re-entry of objects into Earth's atmosphere, and detect and characterise fragmentation events

Figure 6).

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Figure 6: The EU SST service provision (Source: EUSST)

2.1.2.2 Space Weather Events (SWE) monitoring

SWE monitoring focuses on observing and forecasting space weather phenomena, such as solar flares, coronal mass ejections, and geomagnetic storms. These events can disrupt or damage space-based and ground-based infrastructure, including communication and navigation systems, power grids, and pipelines.

2.1.2.3 Near-Earth Object (NEO) tracking

NEO tracking involves the detection and monitoring of asteroids and comets that may pose a collision risk to Earth. This service provides data on the orbits and physical characteristics of NEOs, enabling the assessment of potential impact hazards and the development of mitigation strategies.

3. The European Union Agency for the Space Programme: its role

3.1 EUSPA history and main competences

The origins of the EU Agency for the Space Programme can be traced back to 2002, when the Council Regulation (EC) No 876/2002 set up the Galileo Joint Undertaking (GJU). The main task assigned to this legal entity was the management of the Galileo development phase¹². Later in 2004, the European GNSS Supervisory Authority (GSA) was established by the Council Regulation No 1321/2004, to supervise the development of the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS) and Galileo¹³. GSA officially took over GJU and assumed its tasks on 1 January 2007. In 2010, another change took place since GSA acquired the status of an EU Agency and therefore became the European GNSS Agency as settled by Regulation (EU) No 912/2010. It was entrusted with the Galileo and EGNOS service provision and uptake and its location was set in Prague⁵. The most recent stage in the evolution of the Agency happened in May 2021 when the Regulation (EU) 2021/696 was adopted, establishing the Union Space Programme and EUSPA, which replaced GSA¹.

As specified under Article 29 of the EU Space Programme Regulation, the Agency has tasks such as to ensure the security accreditation of all of the Programme's components through its Security Accreditation Board (SAB), to carry out risk and threat analysis (in particular setting of technical

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specifications and operational procedures) for Galileo and EGNOS, to provide the Commission with its technical expertise, to undertake communication, market development and promotion activities as regards the services offered by Galileo, EGNOS, and Copernicus. In addition, the Agency is entrusted with managing the exploitation of EGNOS and Galileo, coordinating user-related aspects of Governmental Satellite Communications Programme (GOVSATCOM) for the purpose of crisis management missions and operations, with actions in support of an innovative and competitive Union space sector ¹. The European Commission may also decide to entrust the Agency with other tasks in the future.

In order to accomplish the specific tasks specified under Article 29, the Agency ensures the safe and secure management of all space components. In addition, it provides support to research and innovation through various projects such as CASSINI to stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship, and Fundamental Elements and Horizon to increase the EU industry competitiveness. EUSPA additionally engages with market stakeholders to develop innovative and effective applications for Galileo, EGNOS, Govsatcom, as well as leverages synergies between the different components of the Union Space Programme. Furthermore, EUSPA is engaging in promoting the development of applications for the commercialisation of Copernicus and has been operating the Front-Desk of EU SST. The Agency further provides its expertise through in-depth market analysis and ensures that Europe's space-based services are secure, safe, and accessible. ^{14,15,16}

EUSPA engages with multiple partners on the European, national and international levels. The European Commission, and specifically the Directorate General for Defence Industry and Space (DG DEFIS), is in charge of the Union Space Programme and entrusts EUSPA with all its tasks related to Galileo, Copernicus, EGNOS, GOVSATCOM and the Space Situational Awareness (SSA). The European Space Agency (ESA) is also a key partner of EUSPA for the implementation of the Union Space Programme. Furthermore, the Union Space Programme counts several partnerships beyond the EU borders that let it ensure the compatibility and interoperability of the European GNSS with the other constellations around the world. The European Commission, together with the Member States and the European Parliament (as a non-voting Member), is member of the Administrative Board of EUSPA. The EU Member States are also in charge of overseeing the Security Accreditation of the Programme through the Security Accreditation Board, as does the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy ⁵.

Apart from the headquarters in Prague, EUSPA's workforce is present in various sites across Europe (Figure 7): the Galileo Security Monitoring Centre with a site in France and another site in Spain with the EU SST front-desk, the Galileo Reference Centre in the Netherlands, and the European GNSS Service Centre in Spain. The EUSPA EGNOS team is located in France. The Interinstitutional Relations team and the Joint Office are located in Belgium. Additionally, EUSPA manages industrial teams in the Galileo Control Centres based in Italy and Germany, as well as in other facilities ¹⁷.

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Figure 7: EUSPA sites across the EU Member States (Source: EUSPA)

In addition to the current EUSPA sites, the Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/3195¹⁸ focuses on the location of the GOVSATCOM Hub under the EU Space Programme. This decision specifies that the GOVSATCOM Hubs, which are central to organising and managing demand and supply for governmental satellite communications, will be located in two sites: Agios Ioannis in Greece, and Cologne in Germany. Furthermore, the Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2024/1067¹⁹ concerns the implementation of the Union Secure Connectivity Programme, specifically focusing on the location of control centres for the program's ground infrastructure, which will be Toulouse in France, Fucino in Italy, and Bettembourg in Luxembourg.

3.2 The role of EUSPA in security

EUSPA is an agency with security at its core. The role of EUSPA according to the Regulation (EU) 2021/696¹ in security is multifaceted, encompassing governance, operations, and accreditation. The agency acts as a central hub for security-related activities, ensuring the protection of the EU Space Programme's assets and services. The three-pillar structure is elaborated as follows:

Security Governance:

- **Operational Security:** EUSPA is responsible for carrying out all the necessary activities to ensure and monitor the security of Galileo and EGNOS, in particular setting of technical specifications and operational procedures, and monitor their compliance with the general security requirements established by the European Commission. EUSPA supports the European Commission in performing such tasks also for the other Space Programme Components.
- **Security Risks and Threat Analysis:** EUSPA conducts security risk assessments and threat analyses to identify potential vulnerabilities and develop mitigation strategies.

Security Operations:

- **24/7 Monitoring Operations:** EUSPA oversees security monitoring of the EU Space Programme's navigation (Galileo and EGNOS) infrastructure and services to detect and respond to security incidents.
- **Galileo Public Regulated Service Provision with Competent Authorities in EU Member States:** EUSPA ensures, in collaboration with competent authorities in EU Member States, the access management of the Galileo Public Regulated Service.

Security Accreditation Board (SAB):

- **Security Accreditation Authority for All Components of the EU Space Programme:** The SAB, established within the Agency, is the central authority for security accreditation of all

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components of the EU Space Programme. This involves assessing the security posture of systems and services, and granting security accreditation based on compliance with established security standards.

In order to ensure the security and uninterrupted operation of critical space-based services of the EU, the Council Decision (CFSP) 2021/698²⁰ establishes the legal framework for the security of the EU Space Programme. It focuses on securing the EU Space Programme (EUSP) from various threats. It establishes a framework for how the Council of the European Union and the High Representative will respond to security threats affecting the EUSP systems and services. Overall, this Council Decision helps ensure a coordinated and effective response to security threats impacting the critical space infrastructure of the European Union.

In addition, the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence³ calls for an EU Space Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (ISAC). The EU Space ISAC has been established by the European Commission (EC) with the support of EUSPA. It was inaugurated in 2024 and is a network of EU companies from the space sector who are willing to develop their expertise to better prevent, tackle and mitigate security-related challenges, including cybersecurity.

4. The road ahead

The European Commission, under President Ursula von der Leyen, has outlined seven key priorities for its 2024-2029 mandate.²³ These priorities aim to address current challenges and shape a stronger, more resilient Europe for the future. These include a new plan for Europe's sustainable prosperity and competitiveness, a new era for European Defence and Security, supporting people and strengthening societies, sustaining quality of life with a focus on food security, water and nature, protecting democracy and upholding values, leveraging global power and partnerships, and delivering together while preparing the Union for the future.

For the first time there is a dedicated Commissioner for Defence Industry and Space, which underscores the European Union's engagement to elaborate its position in the space domain²⁴. The mission letter the Commissioner received from the President delineates a comprehensive approach, prioritising the implementation of the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence, thereby solidifying the inextricable link between space activities and the Union's broader security framework. Simultaneously, it emphasises the cultivation of a robust and innovative space industry, advocating for autonomous and cost-effective access to space through the strategic development and utilisation of key EU space assets, including Copernicus, Galileo, and GovSatCom/IRIS². A notable emphasis is placed on the development of an EU Space Law, aimed at establishing common standards and licensing procedures. Furthermore, the Commissioner is tasked with formulating a Space Data Economy Strategy, recognising the transformative potential of space-derived data for economic growth and technological advancement. These directives collectively reflect a concerted effort to enhance the EU's strategic autonomy, technological competitiveness, and regulatory coherence within the dynamic and increasingly contested space domain.

Finally, on February 2025, the European Commission provided its perspective on the upcoming Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF)²². It emphasises the necessity for the EU budget to strategically address key policy challenges, including enhancing European competitiveness through research and innovation, and tackling security threats amidst geopolitical tensions. There is a reference to the need for *'Stronger defence readiness, including through space assets, and military mobility is necessary both as a deterrent against future aggression and to support Ukraine towards peace'*. It is highlighted that there is a need for increasing and optimising financing for defence across the EU. The document also calls for a more focused, simpler, and impactful EU budget to ensure that the funds deliver on EU policy priorities.

5. Concluding remarks

The EU's evolving approach to space security reflects a strategic shift from a traditionally civilian-centric policy to one that integrates also key security and defence considerations, as seen in the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence ³ and the Strategic Compass ². In this context, EUSPA plays an increasingly vital role in the EU Space Programme, ensuring the operational security and resilience of key components such as Galileo and EGNOS. Its mandate in security-related applications underscores its contribution to the protection of critical space infrastructure and the delivery of secure services. As counterspace threats, cyber vulnerabilities, and geopolitical tensions grow, the EU continues to enhance the resilience and autonomy of its space infrastructure within the broader security framework ^{23,24}.

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